

Thermal Fatigue by Impact Heating and Stresses of Two Phase Stainless Steel at Elevated Temperature

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Abstract

An experimental study has been made on the behaviours of stresses in each phase of two phase stainless steel at elevated temperature. The stress measurement was carried out by X-ray method which has the characteristic nature of non-contactive and non-destructive.

The residual stress in gamma (f.c.c) phase was measured as tension, and in alpha (b.c.c) phase, as compression at room temperature. When temperature of specimen was increased, these situation of stresses were valied.

A number of heating and cooling cycles from room temperature to higher temperature were imporsed on the specimen of the two phase alloy, the specimen suffered fatigue damage for failure by the thermal stresses.

Introduction

When the temperature of materials is enrised and subsequently cooled, metals and alloys undergo a sequence change of shape that is expansion and compression respectively. If the specimen is at free state having no constraint, no stress should be residued after cooling by uniform heating.

The influence of enrising temperature on crystals of metallic materials are such that recovery, softening, enhanced diffusion of atoms, recrystallization, grain growth and so on. When heating is repeated, these effects must be cummulative.

In considering the number of constructions and equipments, working at high temperature and high pressure, the composing parts are permitted no free expansion and contraction by the restriction from surroundings.

Quantitative understanding of thermal stresses and thermal fatigue phenomena to get optimum design for adequate life of equipments are

This work is partly supported by Grant-in-Aid for Scientific Research, No. 56050041, Ministry of Education, Science and Culture in Japan.

required in the field of nuclear reactor, power generator and chemical processing equipments.

The thermal stresses at increasing temperature have been measured, and the thermal fatigue, caused from repeated heating have been investigated about two phase stainless steel, and have been compared with that of single phase stainless steels. It is noteworthy that the residual stresses were measured as tension in austenite phase and as compression in ferrite phase. The higher the temperature enrised, the lower the stresses become, untill the temperature attained to nearly 600°K. After that temperature, the situation of the stresses were reversed. The residual stresses in single phase stainless steels were reduced with increasing number of heating repetitions, but that in two phase alloys did not reduced and internal fatigue occurred.

The curves of strain against repeated numbers were plotted which were analogous to the curve of creep test, that is "fatigue creep". Curves of applied stresses against repeated numbers were also plotted, the S-N curves were obtained.

One of most interested phenomena was the occurrence of failure under compressive stress, the crack was produced in the normal direction to the specimen axis.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Specimen:

Specimens were prepared as rectangular strips cutted from 1 mm thick plate of SUS 329-J.1 which are composed from two phases, one of which is gamma (f.c.c) phase having lattice constant of $a = 3.59 \times 10^{-10}$ nm, and the other is alpha (b.c.c) phase whose lattice constant is $a = 2.87 \times 10^{-10}$ nm, respectively. And SUS 316 stainless steel was also used to compare the thermal behaviours as a single phase alloy. The chemical components are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Chemical compositions of specimens (mass%)

Materials	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Ni	Cr	Mo	Cu	Ti	Al
SUS 329	0.019	0.54	0.50	0.033	0.006	5.05	23.03	1.52	0.87	0.015	0.019
SUS 316	0.057	0.61	0.87	0.027	0.001	12.18	17.54	2.15	0.26	—	—

Measurement of thermal stresses:

Thermal stresses of each phase in f.c.c phase and in b.c.c phase embeded in two phase stainless steel were measured from the same irradiated area of X-ray beam, using Cr K_{α} radiation. The parallel beam of X-ray were reflected from $\gamma(311)$ and $\alpha(211)$ reflection plane, and $\Delta 2\theta$ were plotted against $\sin^2 \psi$. The tangent of the stright line of the plots give the stress. Calculation of the stress is made by next equation.

$$\sigma = - \frac{E}{1+\nu} \cdot \cot \theta \cdot \frac{\partial 2\theta_{\psi}}{\partial \sin^2 \psi} = KM \quad (1)$$

where θ is Bragg angle, θ_{ψ} is X-ray diffraction angle and K is constant which is the function of elastic moduri of the material. In the case of high temperature problem, elastic modulus E and ν , and lattice constant are the function of temperature, the value of "K" must be decided from experiments. (1)

These value of "K" are plotted in figure 1.

Fig.1 X-ray stress modulus "K" vs temperature curves, of two phase stainless steel

Testing device of thermal fatigue test:

In order to study the thermal fatigue, large number of heating and cooling cycles should be imposed on specimen rapidly. These rapid heating cycles of specimen was carried out by direct passage of large electric current. The block diagram of the apparatus is shown in figure 2. Specimen was firmly installed to the fixed electrode E_1 of its one end and the other end was fixed to movable electrode E_2 , which is slideable on the Cu sliding bed, in the axial direction. The electrode E_2 was pulled or pressed through connecting rod to give tension or compression stress to the specimen. The tensile strain or compressive strain was measured by optical lever system, fitted to the connecting rod. The temperature of specimens were controlled from duration and interval of the current passage, which were regulated by I.C. timer and thyristor circuit.

Fig.2 Apparatus for thermal fatigue, (a) is the block diagram of the circuit and (b) is mechanical device of the test.

OPERATION OF THERMAL CYCLES

The relation of passing duration of electric current is shown in figure 3. After the heating, the specimens were cooled by heat radiation and heat transfer.

The temperature of specimens were reduced to room temperature within about 30 seconds. According to shortening of the intervals of current passage, specimen temperature rised, and it was about 500°K at the interval of 10 second, 850°K at 5 second interval. When the interval of next heating was 2 second, the specimen was melted. These repeated diagram is shown in figure 4.

Fig.3 Passage duration of current vs temperature and cooling time.

Fig.4 Temperature of specimen at various interval of current passage,when the duration is 40/60 second.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thermal stresses of two phases stainless steel:

After residual stresses of two phase alloy at the initial state were measured, temperature of specimens were increased, and the obtained stress from (311) reflection of γ phase was measured as tension of 200 MPa, and that from (211) of α phase was compression of about -140 MPa at room temperature. With increasing temperature, these stresses were reduced tend to zero at nearly 600°K, but after that the situation of the stresses were reversed. These results are plotted in figure 5, and the 2θ vs $\sin^2 \psi$ diagrams are in figure 6.

The residual stress in single phase stainless steel was reduced with increasing number of repeated heating as shown in figure 7, but that in two phase stainless steel did not reduced and internal fatigue should be occurred. The stresses in two phase alloy are shown in figure 8. Thermal fatigue:

In the experiments of thermal fatigue, following process are to be considered.

(1) Specimen is permissible to be extended and contracted: This is no

more than heating and cooling, however, small quantities of compression and tension stress is added by frictional resistance of sliding electrode.

(2) When both electrodes are fixed: Expansion and contraction are constrained and compressive at heating, and tensile at cooling stresses is exerted in specimen.

(3) External tension or compression stress is added: Thermal stress is added to the external stress, but the strain behaviours are complicated.

Figure 9 shows the relation of strain and repeated numbers of heating cycles, one serration gives one cycle of heating and cooling. (experimental mode (1)) Figure 10 shows the strain behaviour of SUS 329-J.1 under tensile stress of 49 MPa (mode (3)), failure was occurred at 50th cycle. Figure 10(b) is that under compression stress of -9.8 MPa. It is very interested that cracking is not confined to tension stress. Figure 11 shows the appearances of fractured part. It is thought that specimens, imposed of thermal cycles under compressive stress were failed by Poisson's deformation which is apparently observed from figure 10(b)

Fig.9 Fatigue-creep strain of SUS 329-J.1 are depicted against repeated numbers

Fig.10 Strain behaviours of SUS 329-J.1, (a) under tension of 49 MPa and (b) under compression of -9.8 MPa.

Applied stress and repeated number of thermal cycles, that are "S-N" curves can be obtained as shown in figure 12. Figure 12 indicates that remarkable acceleration of failures occurred in SUS 329-J.1, owing to large discrepancy of internal stresses between two phases, comparing with SUS 316.

Another one of interesting phenomena is remarkable grain growth during repeated thermal cycles. It can be considered that straining and annealing process were repeated, and the grain size measured in mean diameter of crystal grains are plotted in figure 13. Some photographs of microscopic observation are shown in figure 14.

Fig.11 Fractured appearance of specimen by the thermal fatigue test.

Fig. 5 Stresses of two phase stainless steel SUS 329-L.1, at every elevated temperature

Fig. 8 Internal stresses of two phase alloy, after repetition of thermal cycles

Fig. 6 $2\theta\psi$ - $\sin^2\psi$ diagram, the tangent of the straight line gives "M" in equation (1).

Fig. 7 Stresses of SUS 316 at elevated temperature.

Fig. 12 Applied tensile stresses against repeated number of thermal cycles

Fig. 13 Mean size of crystal grains are plotted against repeated numbers of thermal cycles

Fig.14 Photographs, showing grain growth of
 (a) SUS 329-J1, (b) SUS 316

SUMMARY

Stress and strain behaviours of two phase stainless steel were studied, comparing with single phase stainless steel.

Macroscopic behaviours are the same in both alloys, but the crystallographical stresses and strain are not so at all. The relation of stresses and repeated numbers of heating and cooling cycles of SUS 316 is shown in figure 15 as well as figure 9, that of SUS 329-J.1. These curves are analogous to the creep curve, that is to say the repetition of thermal cycles correspond to fatigue-creep or alternate creep under wide range of temperature.

Fig.15 Strain behaviour of SUS 316 with increasing number of thermal cycles.

In spite of the total period, exposed under high temperature is very short, grain growth is remarkable.

It is thought that a factor of grain growth is predominant in stressing and annealing process. The encroaching mechanism of crystal grains of another phase grains is an interesting problem.

One of causes of shortening of fatigue life may be accounted for internal fatigue which is arisen from large discrepancies of stresses between each phases composing the material.

One of more interesting fact is failure occurred under compression stress, not confined under tension only. It is thought that specimens were pressed and Poisson's deformation occurred at heating process, and tension stress, owing to succeeding cooling, exerted and cracks occurred at some weak points such as transition place.

REFERENCE

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